

Assessment of Digital Literacy and use of Scripted Lesson Plan among Secondary School Teachers in Benin Metropolis, Edo State

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Abstract

The study examined digital literacy and teachers' readiness to employ scripted lesson plans among Secondary Schools in Benin, Edo State. With the availability of a myriad of digital platforms for teachers, traditional techniques of instructing learners still pervade, even when it has become deficient. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population includes all secondary school teachers in public secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Benin Metropolis, Edo State. Sample size of four hundred and fifteen (415) teachers were drawn from the population using proportionate and stratified sampling Technique. A systematic questionnaire (Google form) prepared by the researchers was used to collect data. Two specialists validated the instrument. The reliability coefficients for digital literacy and scripted lessons were 0.786 and 0.813, respectively, using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test indicating the instrument were reliable. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and independent sample t-test statistic were used to examine the data generated. Under the 0.05 threshold of significance, ANOVA was employed to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that there is a favorable and significant association between digital literacy and scripted lessons. The findings further revealed no statistically significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence and preparedness for scripted lessons among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, age and experience. It recommended that government should broaden and deepen its digital literacy training and workshops for in-service teachers through continuous teacher professional development programs.

Key Words: Digital Literacy, Teachers' Preparedness, Scripted Lesson.

Introduction

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in education is crucial in this age of technological innovation and expansion. As a result of technological innovation and expansion, teachers' perceptions of teaching and learning, as well as how they apply the curriculum in classrooms, have changed (Radhakrishnan, DeBoer, & Kimani, 2018). Technology appears to be the answer to more comprehensive and simple teaching and learning. During the 2019-2020 global lockdown induced by the infamous Covid 19, teaching and learning were possible, particularly in difficult regions. To support and facilitate teaching and learning, computers, mobile phones, Skype, teacher tube, Zoom, Google meet, school tube, web windows, video, PowerPoint, and other technologies were used (Duru, Ebere, and Okezie 2022). These E-teaching and Learning systems enable the transmission of instruction and interaction between students and teachers via the Internet (Bubou, Offor, & Job 2021).

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) may have effect on the learning of students if teachers are able to demonstrate digital literacy and comprehend how to blend technology into the curriculum for teaching and learning. In order to communicate, generate, transmit, save, and manage information, schools make use of a wide variety of information and communication technologies (ICT), (Blurton, as cited in Ziad, 2016). In certain contexts, information and communication technology has also become an essential component of the teaching-learning interaction, which includes the substitution of chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, the use of smart phones and tablets by teachers, and the use of students' own smartphones or other devices for learning during class time. Additionally, techniques such as scripted teaching or scripted lesson and flipped classrooms have also become commonplace.

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As part of incorporating technology into education, scripted teaching which refers to an organized teaching and learning process with time allotments for teaching and frequently word-for-word scripts of what the teacher is to teach is advocated.

Also, commercial reading programmes with highly organized lessons, frequently with set time allotments for teaching certain abilities, and often with scripts of the teacher's every word is known as scripted teaching or scripted instruction (Lipson et al., in Mwandia & Mwanza, 2022). Curriculum materials that are scripted are those that have been prepared by professionals and teachers use them to deliver lessons, as it evolved out of an effort to give educators a standard by which to organize and coordinate their work (Doyle, in Mkandawire, 2022).

The language, strategies, and attitudes that make up such a curriculum are essentially instructional scripts that teachers follow. In schools where teachers have not had extensive training, scripted education has been suggested time and time again as a way to standardize the level of instruction (Haruna, 2019). The components of a well-planned lesson include goals for student learning, units or lessons to cover, activities to provide, readings, materials, and methods for evaluating their progress. Opponents of such plans argue that they do not meet the diverse needs of classrooms and that they stifle professional development for educators (Mkandawire, 2022). On the other hand, proponents argue that it is the most straightforward way for educators to impart critical reading skills to their students.

According to Comeyras (quoted in Mkandawire, 2022), scripted instruction has its roots in the 1888 teacher's manual by Samuel and Adeline Monroe, which included reading readiness, phonics, and oral reading scripts. The instructor is expected to adhere strictly to the lesson plans in this style of teaching. The goal of this form of direct instruction is to help educators be more consistent in their lessons. Additionally, it aims at lessening the likelihood of incompetent educators providing inadequate lessons. It is designed to help schools with low standardized test scores by strictly following the script, hence, ensures that students grasp the material better and that lessons are presented consistently.

A common argument against scripted instruction is the belief that anybody can conduct a class as long as they stick to the outline (Commeyras, in Mkandawire 2022). In contrast, some who advocate for scripted instruction submit that, similar to how an actor gives life to a screenplay, a teacher has the power and responsibility to infuse their lessons with authentic content (Commeyras, in Mkandawire, 2022). According to Kohl (quoted in Mwandia and Mwanza, 2021), scripted classes reduce teachers to delivery systems, which in turn lowers instructors' self-esteem and pride in their work because students view them as inanimate objects devoid of critical thinking skills and educational expertise.

There is, however, some literature that support planned lesson/teaching. With test results continuing to plummet and many schools failing to fulfill requirements, many school administrators have turned to scripted curriculum/lesson/teaching to suit regulators/administrators' aims.

Advocates of scripted curriculum claim that employing a scientifically based curriculum will increase student success and enhance standardized test scores. The cornerstone of scripted lessons, according to Gunter and Reed (in Kang 2016), is built on the model, prompt, and check steps to assure subject learning. Scripted curriculum, according to Hiralall and Martens (in Hos et al 2020), may help eliminate disparity in the classroom. Teachers who are unsure about what, when, or how to teach can also benefit from scripted and limited curricula. The author claims that this type of curriculum guarantees that all students, irrespective of their location, the expertise of their teachers, or any other factor, are exposed to the same educational material. Also, according to Walsh in Kang (2016), scripted curriculum advocates believe that teacher-led training is more efficient and predictable when the teacher's statements and the child's expected replies are written. Watkins and Slocum (quoted in Kang, 2016) argue that scripted curricula do two things: first, it guarantees well-designed instruction; and second, it relieves the teacher of the responsibility of creating, evaluating, and improving education for each topic.

According to this author (Kang 2016), scripted programmes offer regular, predictable, organized, and systematic learning environments that can be supervised and trained to assure standardized instruction. Teachers should concentrate on the critical task of providing instruction and overcoming unforeseen circumstances, they stated, and thorough scripts are instruments that help them connect with pupils through the language in the scripts. It is pertinent to state that schools and classrooms employ scripted lesson plans to make up for shortcomings and ensure consistency in subject terminology, since they are designed to incorporate best practices. Scripted programmes, as stated by Boyer (in Kang, 2016), positively affect teaching practices.

Scripted lessons are meant to provide a clear, uniform, and thorough way of teaching that specifies what the instructor will teach, when it will be taught, and how it will be taught (Mwandia & Mwanza, 2022). Some teachers, however, deviate from the pattern that has been supplied to them. In scripted instruction, teachers are given all of the teaching tools, including physical objects, processes, tasks, and concepts. As a result, they lose their independence in the classroom. The lessons serve as a guide for teachers as they go through the process of implementing scripted lessons. It is challenging for educators who are not adept in digital technology to utilize this planned lesson. Students are better prepared to deal with ongoing technological

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change in society and the workplace when teachers are digitally literate and incorporate technology into their teaching (Goodwin, in Eikeland, 2016). The result totally may include that students can develop higher order thinking skills, have more creative and individualized ways to express their understandings, and have more opportunities to express their understandings.

There are teaching technologies as well as learning technologies. Teachers, students, and school administrators are the three key groups who profit the most from technology integration in education. Others include education ministries, future researchers, the corporate sector, and people of society who are less affluent and vulnerable (Keri et al, 2021). However, technology integration in Nigeria, particularly in Benin, has several hurdles. low internet services, low electricity supply, bad economy and its effects, high cost of ICT facilities, scarcity of ICT professionals, unwillingness of instructors, particularly older ones, to change, a lack of maintenance culture, and inadequate locally generated software among other issues. These obstacles make it difficult for teachers to be equipped to apply digital literacy and scripted teaching. These challenges, however, are not enough to discourage determined teachers and government officials who want technological integration in the teaching and learning processes in order to join the digital trend or be digital compliant, necessitating the need to assess teachers' digital literacy and scripted lesson readiness / preparedness in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.

Teachers' Preparedness in Digital Technology

Teachers are under increasing pressure to demonstrate digital competence in response to rising student expectations in the area of technology revolution in education, (Amhag, Hellström, & Stigmar, 2019). Governments worldwide have responded to these insights by launching campaigns and programmes aimed at enhancing educators' digital literacy. For instance, DigCompEdu, the European Framework for Educators' Digital Competence, was developed by the European Union (EU). According to Caena and Redecker (2019), DigCompEdu is a scientific tool that explains how instructors may be digitally proficient from a scientific perspective. Numerous contexts around the world have utilised the DigCompEdu to construct and evaluate digital capabilities (Caena and Redecker, 2019).

Leaving no one behind is the guiding philosophy of the SDGs, or Sustainable Development Goals. Opportunities for lifelong learning and equitable access to high-quality education are emphasised in the fourth Sustainable Development Goal on Quality Education. Teachers must be well-equipped to handle digital content in the classroom in order to keep up with the digital teaching and learning revolution. Students benefit greatly from the utilisation of ICT in the classroom because it enhances their capacity for collaborative learning and fosters the development of transversal skills. These skills are essential for success in the modern world and include, but are not limited to, the following: social awareness, problem solving, independence, responsibility, reflection, and initiative. If educators want to effectively incorporate ICT into their practice in order to navigate the digital age, they must have advanced degrees in teacher preparation. Some Nigerian schools have begun to include ICT into their curricula as a means of making students more tech-savvy, which is crucial for producing critical thinkers who can help their country compete in the global economy. It is necessary to evaluate the level of digital literacy among Edo state teachers as well as their preparedness for digital lessons in secondary schools in the Benin metropolitan area. This is because Edo state is rapidly becoming an e-governance and other e-complaints leader in Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem:

The era of digitalization in all spheres of human endeavours has come to stay. The educational system, particularly, teaching and learning have also been overtaken by this pervasive technological adoption. The successes accruable by the inclusion of these digital devices in educational system have been monumental. But the same success has not been gained in the outcome of students' academic performances in Benin. Hence, implementing digital-based instruction at the secondary school level is critical and this has motivated the government of Edo State to introduce scripted lessons for the entire teachers to be on the same page of lesson preparedness. Unfortunately, majority of these teachers are not literate in the use of Computers and may not have been subjected to in-service training to help them adjust to the modern devices. It is on this premise therefore that the researchers seek to investigate the digital literacy level of teachers and their preparedness of the use of scripted lessons in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis, Edo state where the government is digitally committed.

Objectives of the study:

1. To evaluate the level of digital literacy skills and teachers' preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.
2. To examine if there is difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

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Research Questions:

1. What is the level of digital literacy skill and teachers’ preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis?
2. What is the difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between digital literacy skill and scripted Lesson usage in teaching and learning process among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis
2. There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among public secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

Methodology:

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The Population includes all secondary school teachers in public secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Benin Metropolis, Edo State. Sample size of four hundred and fifteen (415) teachers were drawn from the population using proportionate and stratified sampling Technique. A systematic questionnaire (Google form) prepared by the researchers was used to collect data. Two specialists validated the instrument. The reliability coefficients for digital literacy and scripted lessons were 0.786 and 0.813, respectively, using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test indicating the instrument were reliable. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and independent sample t-test statistic were used to examine the data generated. Under the 0.05 threshold of significance, ANOVA was employed to test the hypotheses.

Results:

Research Question 1

What is the level of digital literacy skill and teachers’ preparedness to use scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis?

Table 1: Description of the level of digital literacy skill of teachers in secondary schools in Benin metropolis

Variable	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Scale mean	Decision
Teachers’ assessment Of their level of digital Literacy skill	415	17558	39.55	9.60	50.00	low

Scale mean = ((4+3+2+1)/4) *20 =50

Table 1. Showed that of the 415 respondents, a mean value of 39.55, standard deviation of 9.60 and a scale mean of 50.00 were obtained. From the result, the mean value is less than the scale means and this indicate that the level of digital literacy skill of teachers in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.

Table 2. Description of the level of preparedness to use of scripted lesson in secondary schools in Benin metropolis

Variable	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Scale mean	Decision
Teachers’ assessment of their level of preparedness to use scripted lessons.	415	11399	25.67	4.14	32.5	low

Scale mean = ((4+3+2+1)/4) *13 =25.67

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Table 2. showed that of the 415 respondents, a mean value of 25.67, standard deviation of 4.14 and a scale mean of 32.5 were obtained. From the result, the mean value is less than the scale means and this indicates that the level of preparedness to use of scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between Digital Literacy skill and scripted lesson usage in teaching learning process of secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis.

Table 3: Correlation results of the relationship between Digital Literacy skill and scripted lesson usage

	Digital literacy	Scripted lesson
Pearson Correlation	1	.748**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	415	415

The result of table 3. reveals that there is a strong positive and significant relation between digital literacy skill and scripted lesson readiness. A breakdown down of the result reveals that the p-value is 0.00 and the correlation coefficient is 0.748 (74.8%). This means that the higher the digital literacy skill, the higher the readiness for scripted lesson

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on sex, age and teaching experience.

Table 4. Independent Sample t- test of Difference between Male and Female teachers in the level of digital literacy skill.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-Cal	p-value
Male teachers	113	1.88	0.33	413	0.46	.114
Female Teachers	302	2.00	0.52			

* *Significant at P< 0.05*

The t-value in Table 4.5 was 0.46, and the p-value was 0.114. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p>0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. Based on this, the null hypothesis was retained, stating that there is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, while the alternative hypothesis, stating that there is a significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender, was rejected. This means that there is no substantial variation in digital literacy skill levels among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.

Table 5. ANOVA test statistic of Difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teaching experience.

ANOVA

Teachers' Experience	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.232	3	.411	1.793	.148
Within Groups	100.744	411	.229		
Total	101.975	414			

The f-value in Table 4.6 was 1.793, and the p-value was 0.148. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p>0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teachers' experience, was

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retained as a result of this. This means that there is no statistically significant variation in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teaching experience.

Table 6. ANOVA test statistic of Difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teachers' age

ANOVA					
Teachers' Age	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.028	3	.676	0.976	.081
Within Groups	99.947	411	.227		
Total	101.975	414			

The f-value in Table 6. was 2.976, and the p-value was 0.081. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p > 0.05$) when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on teachers' age, was retained. This means that there is no statistically significant variation in the degree of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teachers' age.

Findings:

1. The level of digital literacy skill of teachers in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.
2. The level of preparedness to use of scripted lesson in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis is low.
3. There is a strong positive and significant relation between digital literacy skill and scripted lesson readiness.
4. There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis.
5. There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teaching experience.
6. There is no significant difference in the level of digital literacy skill among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on teachers' age

Discussion of Findings:

The findings of this study shows that teachers in public secondary schools in Benin metropolitan have inadequate digital literacy abilities and are ill-prepared to employ scripted lessons. Also, it shows that there is a strong positive and significant relationship among digital literacy competency and scripted lesson. There is no significant difference in digital literacy skills among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolis based on gender. It was also discovered that there is no significant difference in teacher readiness to employ scripted lessons based on gender.

The findings show that public secondary school teachers in Benin City lack digital literacy abilities and are unprepared to adopt scripted teachings. This study contradicts the findings of Kumari and D'Souza (2016), who investigated the usage of ICT in secondary school as well as teachers' digital literacy in India. They discovered that secondary school teachers' ICT use and digital literacy levels were average, however the current study indicated that teachers' digital literacy is low. Furthermore, the findings of Imhanyehor (2021), who investigated the viability of implementing digital literacy in primary schools and determined the availability and accessibility of electronic devices, as well as the barriers to its implementation in private primary schools in Benin City, contradict the findings of this study. According to the study's findings, 90.2% of teachers owned personal computers (PCs) and other electronic devices and were reasonably skilled in their use. This study, however, is consistent with that of Osaat and Nsereka (2012), who used the National Open University of Nigeria as a case study to investigate the effects of ICT on distant learning. They discovered that NOUN had not fully utilised ICT media, indicating that its faculty members were not technologically savvy.

Conversely, this study contradicts the findings of Arnold and Subaveerapandi's (2023) study on the use and purposes of ICT in the classroom, which looked into teachers' digital literacy abilities. Teachers in Zambia have access to digital devices and range in their degree of digital literacy from moderate to high, according to data collected from 20 schools in Lusaka. This study, however, is consistent with Omboto's (2022) investigation into the preparedness of teachers in Nairobi County, Kenya's public primary special schools to implement a digital literacy program. Omboto's study revealed that teachers in Nairobi County's public primary special schools and units were not sufficiently trained to carry out the digital literacy program (DLP) as intended. In contrast, Imhanyehor (2021) conducted research on digital literacy and the Nigerian primary school system and

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discovered that 90.2% of teachers had PCs and other electronic devices and were reasonably adept in using them. This study does not support his findings. Furthermore, this study contradicts the findings of Cote and Milliner (2017), a Japanese university report that surveyed digital literacy among EFL teachers and discovered that the majority of them felt highly comfortable using digital technology to enhance their instruction both within and outside of the classroom. This also holds true for Kumari and D'Souza (2016), who examined the use of ICT in teaching and learning by secondary school teachers in India and found that these aspects of the teachers' profession were mediocre.

Also, the findings show a substantial positive and significant relationship between digital literacy competency and scripted lesson preparedness. This indicates that digital literacy is a prerequisite or presupposes a planned course. Again, findings indicate no significant difference in the degree of digital literacy competence and preparedness for scripted lessons among secondary school teachers in Benin metropolitan based on gender, age, or experience in public secondary schools in Benin metropolis. The findings on teacher age are consistent with those of Keri, et al (2021), who investigated how age affected higher education instructors' use of ICT and discovered that age had no bearing on how teachers used ICT in the classroom. Similarly, Hassan and Abdullah (2013) discovered no statistically significant variations in ICT use between the two teacher groups based on age and experience in their study on the impact of teacher age, experience, and gender on ICT integration in language instruction. This result is consistent with their findings. Additionally, the outcome is consistent with Jegede's (2009) investigation of the ICT attitudes, competency, and use patterns of teacher educators, who discovered that age had no bearing on the amount of time Nigerian higher education instructors spend using ICT.

Regarding teacher experience, the results are inconsistent with those of Ohadiugha (2022), who examined the influence of gender and experience on the ICT skills of senior secondary education teachers, concentrating on ICT skills that facilitate the successful implementation of senior secondary school curricula. Ohadiugha's research revealed that experience plays a major role in the degree of ICT proficiency among teachers. The results of this study, however, are consistent with those of Ibrahim (2016), who examined factors such as gender, years of teaching experience, and educational background as potential indicators of secondary school teachers' proficiency in utilizing ICT in the classroom in Nigeria's Jigawa and Kano states. Ibrahim (2016) discovered that years of teaching experience had no discernible impact on teachers' proficiency in utilizing ICT in the classroom. Similarly, Hassan and Abdullah (2013) looked at how gender, age, and experience of teachers affected the use of ICT in language instruction and discovered no appreciable differences in ICT use between the two groups of instructors according to experience.

Regarding teacher sex and gender, the results of this study are consistent with those of Edeh, et al (2022), who examined gender disparities in teachers' digital literacy in the context of supporting students with functional diversity and found that gender has no appreciable bearing on teachers' abilities in this area. Similarly, the results are consistent with Ohadiugha's (2022) study, which examined the influence of experience and gender on the ICT proficiency of senior secondary education teachers. The study focused on ICT competencies that facilitate the successful implementation of senior secondary school curricula. The results indicated that experience plays a major role in teachers' ICT proficiency, while gender did not. Similarly, Guillén-Gámez, et al (2021) examined the gender gap in higher education teachers' digital competency in research work using a descriptive and comparative analysis, concluding that there were no appreciable differences in teaching staff members' levels of digital competence according to gender.

Additionally, the results of this study are consistent with those of Saibu, et al (2018), who investigated gender disparity and teachers' ICT literacy as predictors of chemistry students' academic performance in Lagos State, Nigeria, and found no relationship between teachers' gender and ICT literacy. The same is true for Ibrahim (2016), who examined years of teaching experience, gender, and educational background as predictors of secondary school teachers' proficiency with ICT in the classroom in the Nigerian states of Jigawa and Kano. The research findings indicate that gender has no bearing on proficiency with ICT. The same is true for Adnan, et al (2013), who looked into how age and gender related to the use of ICT in Pakistani educational institutions and found no relationship between a teacher's gender category and the amount of time they spend on computers each day. The results of this study, however, do not agree with those of Hassan and Abdullah (2013), who examined the impact of gender, age, and experience on ICT integration in language instruction and found that male and female teachers used ICT differently.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, instructors at public secondary schools in Benin metropolitan have a poor level of digital literacy and are less prepared for scripted lessons. In Benin, it was also discovered that there is a favourable and significant association between digital literacy and scripted lessons. As a result, teachers in secondary schools in Benin metropolis should

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be equipped with adequate digital literacy skills in order to effectively and efficiently be prepared or ready for scripted lesson and function effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

- 1) In order to raise the level of digital literacy skills among teachers in Benin City, the current government, which has done a fantastic job of revolutionizing the education sector by introducing technology into teaching and learning, should expand and deepen the workshops and trainings for digital literacy for in-service teachers through ongoing professional development trainings.
- 2) To close the gap, the government should investigate the reasons behind the low level of digital literacy and scripted lesson preparation among public secondary school teachers in Benin City.
- 3) Given the current high cost of living in the state and the country as a whole, the government should subsidize data for the teachers to lessen the financial strain and additional cost required to download scripted lessons from the server.
- 4) All secondary schools in Benin City and the surrounding areas should be able to access the free Wi-Fi that is already available in select areas of the state.
- 5) The government should help secondary school teachers to acquire less expensive android phones to enable the teachers be integrated into digital literacy and scripted lesson.
- 6) In order to keep up with current trends, expectations, and international best practices, the Edo State College of Education and other postsecondary educational institutions in the state tasked with training pre-service teachers ought to modernize their curricula and programs. In particular, they ought to focus on equipping teachers with the skills necessary to teach on any e-platform.
- 7) Due to the 21st century work place skills and expectations, a level of digital literacy competence should be a prerequisite for teacher recruitment into the public service.
- 8) Same study should be extended to other locality within Edo state also.
- 9) Lastly, government of the day should gazette his education reform tagged EdoBEST 2.0 to avoid being abandoned by any subsequent government for continuity and sustainability.

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